

EVALUATING TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE IN RELATION TO JOB SATISFACTION AMONG ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN ORAS WEST DISTRICT: BASIS FOR FORMULATION OF ENHANCED LEARNING DEVELOPMENT PLAN

Benchel M. Picardal¹, Virgilio P. Rapada Jr.²

¹Graduate School, Eastern Samar State University, Borongan City, Eastern Samar, Philippines

²Associate Professor V, Eastern Samar State University, Borongan City, Eastern Samar, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10707072>

Published Date: 26-February-2024

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the performance and job satisfaction of elementary teachers in Oras West District, Oras, Eastern Samar, Philippines. A total of 50 respondents the researcher utilized a survey questionnaire with descriptive correlational research design. To analyze the data, mean scores, percentile rank, frequency count, and Spearman rho correlation coefficient will be used with a 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that the level of job satisfaction of elementary teachers in Oras West District is nearly satisfied with a 3.06 mean score. The job performance of elementary teachers in Oras West District, Oras, Eastern Samar is 100% very satisfactory. There is a significant relationship between the variables (spearman rho = 0.55; p-value = 0.035). However, to encourage elementary teachers in Oras West District in the workplace there is a need to provide financial assistance and harmonious relationships with their co-teachers and school administrators. It is highly recommended to provide necessary technical assistance for the development of the teaching and learning process. Future researchers may conduct a similar study to validate the results of the study.

Keywords: Job performance, development plan, work performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is important and responsible for the development of human resources and in today's competition in the country. It is the long-term investment and the key to a better future for the state and nation (Hartiwi, et.al., 2020). Teachers play a substantial role in the educational system. The success or failure of education in the Philippines is often determined by the performance in implementing the instructional process, promoting classroom management, and learning environment, participation in development and improvement, and encouraging growth and collaboration (Comighud & Arevalo, 2021).

Teacher's performance can be interpreted as the state in which teachers demonstrate their ability to perform their jobs and describe the actions teachers take in the teaching process (Supardi 2014: 54). Therefore, a teacher's performance is related to the teacher's expertise in performing his or her duties. Professional teachers must possess four competencies following the Minister of Education Regulation No. 16 of 2007 on qualifications and competencies. The four competencies a teacher

must have are teaching competency, personal competency, professional competency, and social competency. Among the four competencies that teachers must have, the one that can be explained is the teacher's job performance (Hashana et al., 2019; Salwa et al., 2019)

Moreover, teacher effectiveness is the performance of teachers in carrying out the duties and responsibilities of teachers and educators in schools to optimally achieve specific goals. The teacher's work will be good if he or she has implemented the professional elements of teaching. These learning factors include loyalty and high commitment to teaching, acquisition, and development of teaching materials, discipline in teaching and other work, creativity in teaching, cooperation with school members, leadership as a role model for students, good character, and honesty and it includes authenticity and the purpose is to guide students and fulfill (Hart iwi et al, 2020).

However, Bidartha (2019:94) in the case of Choli believed that teachers' performance in their duties is affected by many factors such as the principal's leadership, job opportunities, expectations, beliefs, and encouragement. Therefore, teacher performance can be affected by internal and external factors.

Hameed et al. (2018) stressed that job satisfaction is an important trait for employees to have in a company or place of work. In an institution, recognizing a person can help them be satisfied with what they are doing. The study concluded that public and private schools differ in job satisfaction due to the following: salary, benefits, and some incentives given by the company. As cited by Polite, 2020 states that "job satisfaction" is an employee's level of satisfaction with the job and other elements of the job. Employees would be more motivated if they had an accomplishment, acknowledgment, and responsibility that they discovered (Hurl, 2018; Polite, 2020).

Furthermore, as cited by Jackson (2018), job satisfaction is an important part of teaching. Teachers can provide students with some necessary items. Job satisfaction can be increased by building a good relationship with a teacher, colleague, supervisor, or manager who will guide them, help meet their needs, and value what they do. A teacher can attain job contentment by combining job satisfiers and decreasing dissatisfiers (Polite 2020).

However, Canzoy (2019) mentioned in his paper that, based on the results of the study, principals' transformative leadership behaviors are more strongly associated with teachers' job satisfaction than interactive leadership behaviors and are a significant predictor of satisfaction. There is a negative correlation between liberating leadership and job satisfaction. Instead, the principal's servant leadership and ethical leadership behaviors were necessary variables for job satisfaction. Finally, research suggests that principals whose organizational behaviors promote participation and flexibility, share leadership in schools, and demonstrate personal and supportive behaviors can increase teacher jobs.

Hence, there is no existing investigation in the Division of Eastern Samar concerning the performance and job satisfaction among Elementary Teachers. The researcher will then conduct a study to have firsthand information on the performance of teachers in their respective schools concerning the job satisfaction of elementary teachers so it can formulate an enhanced development plan for teachers.

Statement of the problem

The study aims to evaluate the relationship between performance and job satisfaction among elementary teachers in Oras West District. It will attempt to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance among elementary teachers in Oras West District?
2. What is the level of job satisfaction among elementary teachers in Oras West District?
3. What is the significance between elementary teachers' performance and job satisfaction in Oras West District?

Significance of the Study

The study's findings should help the administrators of the Oras West District in implementation of development plan and improve the services provided to teachers. By way of understanding the teacher's performance and job satisfaction, specific issues and areas for improvement will be identified as standards. The study has a significant impact on the following several clusters of people who will benefit accordingly:

To the teachers: The results of this study will provide meaningful information on the performance and job satisfaction of the teachers. In addition, administrators will be informed on how they can provide needs that will motivate employees to work effectively and efficiently in their workplace.

To the administrators: The result of the study will focus on improving the performance of the teachers in the workplace.

To the researchers: This study will be valid material for an evaluation purpose. The future study will give new and insightful ideas on how to improve the performance and satisfaction of teachers in school.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This investigation will try to assess and describe the performance and job satisfaction of elementary teachers in Oras West District. Regular -permanent teachers in the Department of Education who are handling a class will be considered as research respondents.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Performance of teachers

The performance of teachers concerns everyone in society (Mbwana, 2015) as cited by (Comighud & Arevalo, 2021) and in this regard, a teacher's performance refers to the responsibility of those teachers to educate students inside and outside the classroom. Core topics of teaching include the use of instructional materials, instruction, continuous student assessment, lesson plan development, student evaluation, work in the field, teacher participation in sports, participation in school assemblies, guidance and discussion. Therefore, the job of a good teacher is about internal and external learning, the ability to integrate knowledge, teaching knowledge, knowledge and skills when teaching content to students. A teacher's performance is measured by regular reporting and participation in school attendance and extra- curricular activities, supervision of school activities, planning of adequate instruction, business planning, instructional planning, grading and punctuality (Comighud & Arevalo, 2021).

Moreover, the performance of teachers in the implementation of education is observed to how well the teacher is prepared for the application and evaluation of the learning process or the teacher's pedagogical knowledge (Morkatik, Harapan, & Wardiah, 2018). However, (Chudi, 2013) as cited by Comighud & Arevalo, 2021 it was found that teachers refused to teach effectively in the classroom, leading to poor performance due to irregular salary payments. Differences in teacher effectiveness between public and private schools are a major concern for policymakers in developing countries. In Tanzania, for example, the best student results come from private schools. In response the government has tried to motivate and retain teachers, especially in rural areas, by giving them incentives despite the popularity of this policy, however, little is known about the actual incentives that motivate teachers and help them perform well despite the challenges of the distance.

Job satisfaction of teachers

The term "job satisfaction" was coined by many researchers. Buluc & Demir (2015) stressed that job satisfaction is a concept that includes employee wages, working conditions, development, opportunities, climate, and job-related expectations. As cited by Wang, Pollock, & Hauseman (2018), the most advanced job satisfaction is a psychological response to the workplace. Job satisfaction is related to how individuals feel about their employment or work (Bhat, 2018). Job satisfaction is defined as an employee's level of satisfaction with his job and other aspects of his job (Polite, 2022).

School factors had no significant impact on performance but teachers had a greater impact on students earning job satisfaction, while parents were actively engaged in supporting, providing, and sustaining adequate learning materials (Anabo, 2023).

According to Locke (cited in Tien, 2018), research on employee attitudes toward work is beginning to add significantly more information about the factors that contribute to happiness and employee dissatisfaction. Teachers in the United States are increasingly dissatisfied with their jobs for various reasons (Von Fischer & De Jong, 2017). Job satisfaction literature encourages teachers who focus on inaction. Decision-making, stress caused by increased responsibilities, a negative school climate, and a lack of support from school leaders are factors that affect teacher satisfaction (Von Fischer & De Jong, 2017).

School programs the teachers to open new schools have the potential of the learners and teachers to job satisfaction and work performance (Anabo, R. O., et.al., 2023). Teachers are the backbone of the educational system, says Abdulahi (2020). These are big numbers that need to keep growing (p. 152). Research has shown that job satisfaction and unhappiness are functions of perceptions of the relationship between job expectations and what they bring, the study states (Locke, 1969, p. 10). However, there are still several critical gaps to address regard, as the performance of teachers continues to report that they cannot find interesting in the skills required for today's advanced workplaces (Jamer; F.T. & Anabo, R.O. (2023).

According to research, teachers show varying levels of satisfaction based on communication with principals (Green & Muoz, 2016). In addition, (Bhat, 2018; Okeke & Mtyunda, 2017) mentioned in their paper that teacher job satisfaction is crucial, especially at the secondary level. According to the Society of Human Resource Management (2016), "In 2015, 88

percent of American workers were satisfied, and 51 percent were somewhat satisfied." Teachers have invested a lot of time and money into their work. It is very important that teachers are satisfied with their work. Job satisfaction is defined as a teacher's good or bad attitude towards a student or school (Yavuz, 2018) and is measured by management, peers, working conditions (Ghavifekr & Pillai, 2016), salary, responsibility, job, safety, and gratitude (Belias, 2014). Finally, satisfied teachers have higher levels of engagement and are less likely to leave.

Theoretical Framework

This study is supported by the theory of Frederick Herzberg (1950) was known as a pioneer of motivation theory. He interviewed a group of employees to find out what made them happy about their jobs. In these interviews, Herzberg discovered two dimensions of job satisfaction: motivation and hygiene. Hygiene problems do not motivate employees, but they can reduce dissatisfaction if managed properly. In particular, frustration can arise if it is used incorrectly. Hygiene dimensions include policy, supervision, pay, interpersonal relations, and working conditions. They are related to the client environment. Instead, motivation creates satisfaction by satisfying employees' goals and personal development needs, including their performance, growth progress, recognition, responsibility, and the work itself. Addressing hygiene issues ultimately increases motivation, job satisfaction, and productivity. The first theory that examines the most important factors that affect a person's job satisfaction is Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory. This is well known in motivational literature. The five-level hierarchy of needs includes physiological needs, safety needs, belongingness/love, esteem, and self-actualization. However, it is the primary use of job readiness and has been used to describe job satisfaction. Financial rewards and wellness services are among the benefits that help employees meet their physical needs. Safety needs can be met by making employees feel safe in their work environment. Employees can focus on their work once they have been granted permission. This can be seen in building positive relationships with co-workers, supervisors, managers, and administrators. Once this is done, the employee will strive to do his job better because he feels valued and appreciated by his organization and colleagues. Ultimately, the goal of employees is self-actualization; they have to grow and move forward to become who they can be. Finally, John Locke's value theory suggests that job satisfaction is related to individual expectations, job performance, and effort. Job satisfaction will increase as employees move closer to achieving their goals. Like Herzberg's theory, job satisfaction comes from results and outcomes. Specifically, Locke's theory of value depends entirely on the outcome of a function (Gonzales et al., 2022).

Conceptual Framework

Teachers are viewed as change agents in the classroom. They give their best to deliver quality education to learners and the community they live in. Despite the adverse situation faced by teachers nowadays, they need to give the best performance in their work and need to adapt to global change in the academe. Teachers can enhance self-efficacy, confidence, discipline, and motivation with the help of family, co-workers, the school principal, and friends as well.

A teacher must be recognized by his or her school head to be satisfied with his or her work. This will encourage them to do more and give more because they feel they are valued by their actions. With this investigation, it is necessary to assess performance and job satisfaction among elementary teachers in Oras West District. Specific issues will be given attention by school administrators about the conditions of teachers in the field.

The following schema diagrammatically illustrates the relationship between the variables that will be considered in the study:

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram

III. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Research design

This study will be using descriptive and correlational methods, specifically the quantitative research design. The design will be deemed appropriate in describing the respondents' profile characteristics, the relationship between teachers' performance and job satisfaction, and the discovery of a correlation between the independent and dependent variables. As cited by Shuttleworth (2008) in his paper, descriptive research is designed as a systematic method to observe and describe human behavior without influencing it in any way.

Respondents and locale of the study

The study was conducted in 20 elementary schools and a total of 50 respondents in the Oras West District, Oras, Eastern Samar. The researcher employed simple random sampling and filled out the survey questionnaire.

Data collection method

To arrive at the exact data to be used in this study, a researcher-modified questionnaire will be utilized. The instrument will be divided into two (2) parts according to the research objectives, as follows: Part I, Teacher Level of job satisfaction, and Part II, Teachers' Level of Performance. To ensure the reliability of the said instrument, a reliability test will be conducted by the researchers.

Analysis of data

Indicating that any observed effects or relationships with a probability of occurring by chance less than 5% would be considered statistically significant. The researcher made use of frequency count and percentage. Finally, the multiple hierarchical regression analysis was employed to predict which model can significantly predict the criterion variable.

Ethical consideration

The study adhered to the relevant research ethics guidelines, and consent forms were provided to the participants and collected accordingly. Additionally, a permit was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent of Eastern Samar Division. The respondent was assured that their data would be treated confidentially.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Level of Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Indicators	Mean score	Rank	Level of Job Satisfaction
1. My dedication to work and feeling secure in my job is essential.	2.15	8	Nearly Satisfied
2. The availability of appropriate educational means increases my job satisfaction towards work.	3.65	3	Nearly Satisfied
3. I feel satisfied with my job.	2.67	5	Nearly Satisfied
4. My teaching experience satisfied me to work.	1.45	10	Satisfied
5. The job description helps me keep working and satisfied.	2.34	7	Nearly Satisfied
6. Financial incentives improve my job performance at work.	5.45	1	Dissatisfied
7. My work has allowed me to build relationships with my co-workers.	3.83	4	Nearly Satisfied
8. I volunteer to do extra work to serve the school.	2.54	6	Nearly Satisfied
9. Good supervision by the school head reduces my job satisfaction towards work.	1.98	9	Satisfied
10. I get praise from my school head when I do well.	4.56	2	Dissatisfied
Total	3.06		Nearly Satisfied

Table 1 presents the level of job satisfaction of elementary teachers of Oras West District, the statement “Financial incentives improve my job performance at work” got the highest mean score of 5.45 with a dissatisfied level of job performance. It implies that the elementary teachers in Oras West District, Oras Eastern Samar need a salary increase, and give importance to the quality of education, for the job satisfaction to teach at school. The “My teaching experience satisfied me to work.” gets the lowest mean score of 1.45 with a satisfied level of job satisfaction the overall mean score is 3.06 interpreted as “Nearly Satisfied” level of job satisfaction of elementary teachers in Oras West District, Oras Eastern Samar, Philippines.

Table 2. Level of Teachers’ Performance

Adjectival rating	Description	Frequency	Percent
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	0	0
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	50	100
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	0	0
1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory	0	0
below 1.499	Poor	0	0
Total		50	100

Table 2 shows the level of teachers’ performance of elementary teachers in Oras West District, Oras Eastern Samar, Philippines. Results reveal that 50 or 100% of the elementary teachers’ respondents acquired a very satisfactory performance rating, Similarly, Baluyos, et.al., (2019) reported a very satisfactory work performance of the teacher respondents. The results imply that teachers’ level of performance was able to carry their work very satisfactorily in the teaching-learning process. Promote parents and community participation to continue professional development.

Table 3. A significant difference between the level of job satisfaction, teachers' performance, and Learning Development Plan

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	rho	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of job satisfaction						
Level of Teachers’ Performance	Learning Development Plan	0.55	Strong	0.035	Reject H ₀	Significant

$\alpha = 0.05, df = 2$

Table 3 shows the relationship between the level of job satisfaction, teachers’ performance, and learning development plan. The result reveals that 0.55 Spearman rho with a strong relationship between the two variables, the p-value of 0.035 rejected the null hypotheses and interpreted as there is a significant relationship between the level of job satisfaction, teachers’ performance, and learning development plan.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Based on the results, it was concluded that the “Nearly Satisfied” level of job satisfaction of elementary teachers in Oras West District, Oras, Eastern Samar, Philippines, and all of them are very satisfactory teachers’ performance. Based on the relationship between the variables there was a significant relationship (spearman rho = 0.55; p-value = 0.026) between the level of job satisfaction, teachers’ performance, and learning development plan.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are presented:

1. To improve job satisfaction of elementary teachers in Oras West District, Oras, Eastern Samar in the workplace by providing financial assistance.

2. Provide the necessary skills in learning development.
3. The school head should provide technical assistance.
4. Future researchers may conduct a similar study to validate the results of the study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anabo, R.O. (2023). Correlates of mathematics performance of grade 9 learners in secondary schools division of Eastern Samar amidst pandemic. *EPR International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*. 9(6). <https://doi.org/10.36713/epri13649>
- [2] Anabo, R. O., Rivera, B. H., Agustin, V. L. G., & Agda, V. A. (2023). Feasibility Study of Establishing Junior High School “Roy Anabo Memorial National High School (RAMNHS)” in Dolores, Eastern Samar. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 6(8), 36–39. Retrieved from <https://journal.ijresm.com/index.php/ijresm/article/view/2772>
- [3] Baluyos, G. R., Rivera, H. L., & Baluyos, E. L. (2019). Teachers’ job satisfaction and work performance. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(08), 206. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=94433>
- [4] Department of Education (2020). DepEd prepares Self-Learning Modules for education’s new normal. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/07/02/depedprepares-selflearning-modules-for-educationsnew-normal/>
- [5] Fisher, M. H. (2011). Factors Influencing Stress, Burnout, and Retention of Secondary Teachers. *Current Issues in Education*, 14(1).
- [6] Gu, Q., & Li, Q (2013). Sustaining resilience in times of change: Stories from Chinese teachers. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 41(3), 288-303
- [7] Howard, S. K. & Johnson, B. (2018). Resilient teachers: resisting stress and burnout. *Social Psychology of Education*, 7(4), 399-420.
- [8] Jamer; F.T. & Anabo, R.O. (2023). Add-on Subjects in Science Special Program-Science, Technology, Engineering (STE): Its Impact in Choosing a Career in STEM. Volume. 8 Issue. 12, December - 2023 *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology (IJISRT)*, www.ijisrt.com. ISSN - 2456-2165, PP: - 1754-1757. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10453900>
- [9] Jackson, M.J. (2018). Examining the Relationship between School Climate and Teacher Absenteeism, Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teachers’ Intentions to Remain. Proquest Dissertation Publishing
- [10] Keshavarz, M. & Mohammadi, R. (2021). Occupational stress and Organizational performance, Case study: Iran. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 390-394, [10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.077](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.077).
- [11] Mansfield, C.F., Beltman, S. Weatherby-Fell, N., & Broadley, T. (2016). Classroom ready? Building resilience in teacher education. *Teacher Education: Innovation, intervention and impact*. Singapore
- [12] Mclean, L.; Taylor, M.; Abry, T. & Jimenez, M. (2017). Teachers' Mental Health and Perceptions of School Climate Across the Transition from Training to Teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education* 65, 230-240.
- [13] Oco, R. (2022). Level of job satisfaction of public high school teachers: A survey. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 95. DOI: 10.47119/IJRP100951220222888